

ON THE STRUCTURE OF SETS WHICH HAVE COINCIDING REPRESENTATION FUNCTIONS

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Abstract

For a set of nonnegative integers A , denote by $R_A(n)$ the number of unordered representations of the integer n as the sum of two different terms from A . In this paper we partially describe the structure of the sets, which have coinciding representation functions.

1. Introduction

Let $\mathbb{N}$ denote the set of nonnegative integers. For a given set $A \subseteq \mathbb{N}$, $A = \{a_1, a_2, \dots\}$ ($0 \leq a_1 < a_2 < \dots$), the additive representation functions $R_{h,A}^{(1)}(n)$, $R_{h,A}^{(2)}(n)$ and $R_{h,A}^{(3)}(n)$ are defined in the following way:

$$R_{h,A}^{(1)}(n) = |\{(a_{i_1}, \dots, a_{i_h}) : a_{i_1} + \dots + a_{i_h} = n, a_{i_1}, \dots, a_{i_h} \in A\}|,$$

$$R_{h,A}^{(2)}(n) = |\{(a_{i_1}, \dots, a_{i_h}) : a_{i_1} + \dots + a_{i_h} = n, a_{i_1} \leq a_{i_2} \leq \dots \leq a_{i_h}, a_{i_1}, \dots, a_{i_h} \in A\}|,$$

$$R_{h,A}^{(3)}(n) = |\{(a_{i_1}, \dots, a_{i_h}) : a_{i_1} + \dots + a_{i_h} = n, a_{i_1} < a_{i_2} < \dots < a_{i_h}, a_{i_1}, \dots, a_{i_h} \in A\}|.$$

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For simplicity we write $R_{2,A}^{(3)}(n) = R_A(n)$. If A is finite, let $|A|$ denote the cardinality of A .

The investigation of the partitions of the set of nonnegative integers with identical representation functions was a popular topic in the last few decades [1,3,4,5,7,9,11, 13,14]. It is easy to see that $R_{2,A}^{(1)}(n)$ is odd if and only if $\frac{n}{2} \in A$. It follows that for every positive integer n , $R_{2,C}^{(1)}(n) = R_{2,D}^{(1)}(n)$ holds if and only if $C = D$, where $C = \{c_1, c_2, \dots\}$ ($c_1 < c_2 < \dots$) and $D = \{d_1, d_2, \dots\}$ ($d_1 < d_2 < \dots$) are two sets of nonnegative integers. In [8], Nathanson gave a full description of the sets C and D , which have identical representation functions $R_{2,C}^{(1)}(n) = R_{2,D}^{(1)}(n)$ from a certain point on. Namely, he proved the following theorem. Let $C(z) = \sum_{c \in C} z^c$, $D(z) = \sum_{d \in D} z^d$ be the generating functions of the sets C and D , respectively.

Theorem 1. *Let C and D be different infinite sets of nonnegative integers. Then $R_{2,C}^{(1)}(n) = R_{2,D}^{(1)}(n)$ holds from a certain point on if and only if there exist positive integers n_0, M and finite sets of nonnegative integers F_C, F_D, T with $F_C \cup F_D \subset [0, Mn_0 - 1]$, $T \subset [0, M - 1]$ such that*

$$\begin{aligned} C &= F_C \cup \{lM + t : l \geq n_0, t \in T\}, \\ D &= F_D \cup \{lM + t : l \geq n_0, t \in T\}, \\ 1 - z^M &|(F_C(z) - F_D(z))T(z). \end{aligned}$$

We conjecture in [6] that the above theorem of Nathanson can be generalized in the following way.

Conjecture 1. *For $h > 2$ let C and D be different infinite sets of nonnegative integers. Then $R_{h,C}^{(1)}(n) = R_{h,D}^{(1)}(n)$ holds from a certain point on if and only if there exist positive integers n_0, M and finite sets F_C, F_D, T with $F_C \cup F_D \subset [0, Mn_0 - 1]$, $T \subset [0, M - 1]$ such that*

$$\begin{aligned} C &= F_C \cup \{lM + t : l \geq n_0, t \in T\}, \\ D &= F_D \cup \{lM + t : l \geq n_0, t \in T\}, \\ (1 - z^M)^{h-1} &|(F_C(z) - F_D(z))T(z)^{h-1}. \end{aligned}$$

For $h = 3$, Kiss, Rozgonyi and Sándor proved [6] Conjecture 1. In the general case when $h > 3$ we proved that if the conditions of Conjecture 1 hold then $R_{h,C}^{(1)}(n) = R_{h,D}^{(1)}(n)$ holds from a certain point on. Later, Rozgonyi and Sándor [10] proved that the above conjecture holds when $h = p^\alpha$, where $\alpha \geq 1$ and p is a prime.

It is easy to see that for any two different sets $C, D \subset \mathbb{N}$ we have $R_{2,C}^{(2)}(n) \neq R_{2,D}^{(2)}(n)$ for some $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Let i denote the smallest index for which $c_i \neq d_i$, thus we may assume that $c_i < d_i$. It is clear that $R_{2,C}^{(2)}(c_1 + c_i) > R_{2,D}^{(2)}(c_1 + c_i)$, which implies that there exists a nonnegative integer n such that $R_{2,C}^{(2)}(n) \neq R_{2,D}^{(2)}(n)$. We pose a problem about this representation function.

Problem 1. Determine all the sets of nonnegative integers C and D such that $R_{2,C}^{(2)}(n) = R_{2,D}^{(2)}(n)$ holds from a certain point on.

In this paper, we focus on the representation function $R_A(n)$. We partially describe the structure of the sets, which have identical representation functions. To do this, we define the Hilbert cube which plays a crucial role in our results. Let $\{h_1, h_2, \dots\}$ ($h_1 < h_2 < \dots$) be finite or infinite set of positive integers. The set

$$H(h_1, h_2, \dots) = \left\{ \sum_i \varepsilon_i h_i : \varepsilon_i \in \{0, 1\} \right\}$$

is called the Hilbert cube. The even part of a Hilbert cube is the set

$$H_0(h_1, h_2, \dots) = \left\{ \sum_i \varepsilon_i h_i : \varepsilon_i \in \{0, 1\}, 2 \mid \sum_i \varepsilon_i \right\},$$

and the odd part of a Hilbert cube is

$$H_1(h_1, h_2, \dots) = \left\{ \sum_i \varepsilon_i h_i : \varepsilon_i \in \{0, 1\}, 2 \nmid \sum_i \varepsilon_i \right\}.$$

We say a Hilbert cube $H(h_1, h_2, \dots)$ is half non-degenerated if the representation of any integer in $H_0(h_1, h_2, \dots)$ and $H_1(h_1, h_2, \dots)$ is unique, that is $\sum_i \varepsilon_i h_i \neq \sum_i \varepsilon'_i h_i$ whenever $\sum_i \varepsilon_i \equiv \sum_i \varepsilon'_i \pmod 2$, where $\varepsilon'_i \in \{0, 1\}$.

Many years ago, Selfridge and Straus [12] proved the following theorem about the cardinality of sets with identical representation functions. For the sake of completeness, we present the proof in Section 2.

Theorem 2. *Let C and D be different finite sets of nonnegative integers such that for every positive integer n , $R_C(n) = R_D(n)$ holds. Then we have $|C| = |D| = 2^l$ for a nonnegative integer l .*

If $0 \in C$ and for $D = \{d_1, d_2, \dots\}$, $0 \leq d_1 < d_2 < \dots$, we have $R_C(m) = R_D(m)$ (sequences C and D are different), then $d_1 > 0$. Otherwise let us suppose that $c_i = d_i$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots, n-1$, but $c_n < d_n$ which implies that $R_C(c_1 + c_n) > R_D(c_1 + c_n)$, a contradiction.

If $|C| = |D| = 1$ and $0 \in C$ with $R_C(n) = R_D(n)$, then we have $C = \{0\}$ and $D = \{d_1\}$. Therefore, $C = H_0(d_1)$ and $D = H_1(d_1)$.

If $|C| = |D| = 2$ and $0 \in C$ with $R_C(n) = R_D(n)$, then $C = \{0, c_2\}$ and $D = \{d_1, d_2\}$. In this case $1 = R_C(0 + c_2)$, and for $n \neq c_2$ we have $R_C(n) = 0$. Moreover, $1 = R_C(d_1 + d_2)$ and for $n \neq d_1 + d_2$ we have $R_D(n) = 0$. This implies that $d_1 + d_2 = c_1 + c_2 = c_2$, that is $C = \{0, d_1 + d_2\} = H_0(d_1, d_2)$ and $D = \{d_1, d_2\} = H_1(d_1, d_2)$.

If $|C| = |D| = 4$ and $0 \in C$ with $R_C(n) = R_D(n)$, then let $C = \{c_1, c_2, c_3, c_4\}$, $c_1 = 0$ and $D = \{d_1, d_2, d_3, d_4\}$, where $d_1 > 0$. Then we have

$$c_1 + c_2 < c_1 + c_3 < c_1 + c_4, c_2 + c_3 < c_2 + c_4 < c_3 + c_4$$

and

$$d_1 + d_2 < d_1 + d_3 < d_1 + d_4, d_2 + d_3 < d_2 + d_4 < d_3 + d_4,$$

which implies that $c_1 + c_2 = d_1 + d_2$. Therefore, $c_2 = d_1 + d_2$ and $c_1 + c_3 = d_1 + d_3$, thus we have $c_3 = d_1 + d_3$. If $c_2 + c_3 = d_2 + d_3$, then $(d_1 + d_2) + (d_1 + d_3) = d_2 + d_3$, that is $d_1 = 0$, a contradiction. Hence $c_2 + c_3 = d_1 + d_4$, that is $(d_1 + d_2) + (d_1 + d_3) = d_1 + d_4$. This implies that $d_4 = d_1 + d_2 + d_3$. Finally $c_1 + c_4 = d_2 + d_3$, that is $c_4 = d_2 + d_3$. Thus we have $C = \{0, d_1 + d_2, d_1 + d_3, d_2 + d_3\} = H_0(d_1, d_2, d_3)$ and $D = \{d_1, d_2, d_3, d_1 + d_2 + d_3\} = H_1(d_1, d_2, d_3)$. In the next step we prove that if the sets are even and odd parts of a Hilbert cube, then the corresponding representation functions are identical.

Theorem 3. *Let $H(h_1, h_2, \dots)$ be a half non-degenerated Hilbert cube. If $C = H_0(h_1, h_2, \dots)$ and $D = H_1(h_1, h_2, \dots)$, then for every positive integer n , $R_C(n) = R_D(n)$ holds.*

It is easy to see that Theorem 3 is equivalent to Lemma 1 of Chen and Lev in [2]. First, they proved the finite case $H(h_1, \dots, h_n)$ by induction on n , and the infinite case was a corollary of the finite case. For the sake of completeness, we give a different proof by using generating functions. Chen and Lev asked whether Theorem 3 described all different sets C and D of nonnegative integers such that $R_C(n) = R_D(n)$. The following conjecture is a simple generalization of the above question formulated by Chen and Lev but we use a different terminology.

Conjecture 2. Let C and D be different infinite sets of nonnegative integers with $0 \in C$. If for every positive integer n , $R_C(n) = R_D(n)$ holds, then there exist positive integers $d_{i_1}, d_{i_2}, \dots \in D$, where $d_{i_1} < d_{i_2} < \dots$, and a half non-degenerated Hilbert cube $H(d_{i_1}, d_{i_2}, \dots)$ such that

$$C = H_0(d_{i_1}, d_{i_2}, \dots),$$

$$D = H_1(d_{i_1}, d_{i_2}, \dots).$$

We showed above that Conjecture 2 is true for the finite case $l = 0, 1, 2$. Unfortunately we could not settle the cases $l \geq 3$, which seems to be very complicated. In Section 4 we prove the following weaker version of the above conjecture.

Theorem 4. *Let $D = \{d_1, \dots, d_{2^n}\}$, $(0 < d_1 < d_2 < \dots < d_{2^n})$ be a set of nonnegative integers, where $d_{2^{k+1}} \geq 4d_{2^k}$, for $k = 0, \dots, n - 1$ and $d_{2^k} \leq d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + d_5 + \dots + d_{2^{i+1}} + \dots + d_{2^{k-1+1}}$ for $k = 2, \dots, n$. Let C be a finite set of nonnegative integers such that $0 \in C$. If for every positive integer m , $R_C(m) = R_D(m)$ holds, then*

$$C = H_0(d_1, d_2, d_3, d_5, \dots, d_{2^k+1}, \dots, d_{2^{n-1}+1}),$$

and

$$D = H_1(d_1, d_2, d_3, d_5, \dots, d_{2^k+1}, \dots, d_{2^{n-1}+1}).$$

For any sets of nonnegative integers A and B we define the sumset $A + B$ by

$$A + B = \{a + b : a \in A, b \in B\}.$$

The special case $b + A$ denotes the set $\{b + a : a \in A\}$, where b is a fixed nonnegative integer. Let $q\mathbb{N}$ denote the dilate of the set $\mathbb{N}$ by the factor q , that is, $q\mathbb{N}$ is the set of nonnegative integers divisible by q . Let $r_{A+B}(n)$ denote the number of solutions of the equation $a + b = n$, where $a \in A, b \in B$. In [2], Chen and Lev proved the following nice result.

Theorem 5. *Let l be a positive integer. Then there exist sets C and D of nonnegative integers such that $C \cup D = \mathbb{N}$, $C \cap D = 2^{2l} - 1 + (2^{2l+1} - 1)\mathbb{N}$ and for every positive integer n , $R_C(n) = R_D(n)$ holds.*

This theorem is an easy consequence of Theorem 3 by putting

$$H(1, 2, 4, 8, \dots, 2^{2l-1}, 2^{2l} - 1, 2^{2l+1} - 1, 2(2^{2l+1} - 1), 4(2^{2l+1} - 1), 8(2^{2l+1} - 1), \dots).$$

The details can be found in the first part of the proof of Theorem 6. Chen and Lev [2] formulated the following conjecture.

Conjecture 3. Let C and D be different sets of nonnegative integers such that $C \cup D = \mathbb{N}$, $C \cap D = r + m\mathbb{N}$ with integers $r \geq 0, m \geq 2$. If for every positive integer n , $R_C(n) = R_D(n)$ holds, then there exists an integer $l \geq 1$ such that $r = 2^{2l} - 1$ and $m = 2^{2l+1} - 1$.

We formulate the following conjecture, which is a stronger version of the above conjecture of Chen and Lev.

Conjecture 4. Let C and D be different sets of nonnegative integers such that $C \cup D = \mathbb{N}$, $C \cap D = r + m\mathbb{N}$ with integers $r \geq 0, m \geq 2$. If for every positive integer n , $R_C(n) = R_D(n)$ holds, then there exists an integer $l \geq 1$ such that

$$C = H_0(1, 2, 4, 8, \dots, 2^{2l-1}, 2^{2l} - 1, 2^{2l+1} - 1, 2(2^{2l+1} - 1), 4(2^{2l+1} - 1), 8(2^{2l+1} - 1), \dots),$$

and

$$D = H_1(1, 2, 4, 8, \dots, 2^{2l-1}, 2^{2l} - 1, 2^{2l+1} - 1, 2(2^{2l+1} - 1), 4(2^{2l+1} - 1), 8(2^{2l+1} - 1), \dots).$$

We prove that Conjecture 2 implies Conjecture 4.

Theorem 6. *Assume that Conjecture 2 holds. Then there exist C and D , different infinite sets of nonnegative integers, such that $C \cup D = \mathbb{N}$, $C \cap D = r + m\mathbb{N}$ with integers $r \geq 0, m \geq 2$ and for every positive integer n , $R_C(n) = R_D(n)$ if and only if there exists an integer $l \geq 1$ such that*

$$C = H_0(1, 2, 4, 8, \dots, 2^{2l-1}, 2^{2l} - 1, 2^{2l+1} - 1, 2(2^{2l+1} - 1), 4(2^{2l+1} - 1), 8(2^{2l+1} - 1), \dots)$$

and

$$D = H_1(1, 2, 4, 8, \dots, 2^{2l-1}, 2^{2l} - 1, 2^{2l+1} - 1, 2(2^{2l+1} - 1), 4(2^{2l+1} - 1), 8(2^{2l+1} - 1), \dots).$$

2. Proof of Theorem 2

Proof. By using the generating functions of the sets C and D , we get that

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} R_C(n)z^n = \frac{C(z)^2 - C(z^2)}{2},$$

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} R_D(n)z^n = \frac{D(z)^2 - D(z^2)}{2}.$$

It follows that

$$R_C(n) = R_D(n) \text{ if and only if } C(z)^2 - D(z)^2 = C(z^2) - D(z^2). \tag{1}$$

Let $l + 1$ be the largest exponent of the factor $(z - 1)$ in $C(z) - D(z)$, i.e.,

$$C(z) - D(z) = (z - 1)^{l+1}p(z), \tag{2}$$

where $p(z)$ is a polynomial and $p(1) \neq 0$. Substituting (2) back to (1) gives

$$(C(z) + D(z))(z - 1)^{l+1}p(z) = (z^2 - 1)^{l+1}p(z^2).$$

Then we have $(C(z) + D(z))p(z) = (z + 1)^{l+1}p(z^2)$. Substituting $z = 1$, we have $C(1) + D(1) = 2^{l+1}$, which implies that $|C| + |D| = 2^{l+1}$. On the other hand,

$$\binom{|C|}{2} = \sum_m R_C(m) = \sum_m R_D(m) = \binom{|D|}{2},$$

which gives $|C| = |D|$. □

3. Proof of Theorem 3

Proof. By (1) we have to prove that $C(z)^2 - D(z)^2 = C(z^2) - D(z^2)$. It is easy to see from the definition of C and D that

$$\prod_i (1 - z^{h_i}) = \sum_{i_1 < \dots < i_t} (-1)^t z^{h_{i_1} + \dots + h_{i_t}} = C(z) - D(z).$$

On the other hand, clearly we have $C(z) + D(z) = \prod_i (1 + z^{h_i})$. Then we have

$$\begin{aligned} C(z)^2 - D(z)^2 &= (C(z) - D(z))(C(z) + D(z)) = \prod_i (1 - z^{h_i}) \cdot \prod_i (1 + z^{h_i}) \\ &= \prod_i (1 - z^{2h_i}) = C(z^2) - D(z^2). \end{aligned}$$

The proof is completed. □

4. Proof of Theorem 4

We apply induction on n . If $n = 0$, then $C = \{0\}$ and $D = \{d_1\}$. Therefore, for every positive integer m , we have $R_C(m) = R_D(m) = 0$. If $n = 1$, then $C = \{0, c_2\}$ and $D = \{d_1, d_2\}$. Since $R_C(m) = R_D(m)$ for every positive integer m , it follows that $R_D(d_1 + d_2) = 1 = R_C(d_1 + d_2)$. Then we have $C = \{0, d_1 + d_2\} = H_0(d_1, d_2)$ and $D = \{d_1, d_2\} = H_1(d_1, d_2)$. Assume that the statement of Theorem 4 holds for $n = N - 1$. We will prove it for $n = N$. Let $D = \{d_1, \dots, d_{2^N}\}$ be a set of nonnegative integers, where $d_{2^{k+1}} \geq 4d_{2^k}$, for $k = 0, \dots, N - 1$ and $d_{2^k} \leq d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + d_5 + \dots + d_{2^i+1} + \dots + d_{2^{k-1}+1}$ for $k = 2, \dots, N$. If C is a set of nonnegative integers such that $0 \in C$ and for every positive integer m , $R_C(m) = R_D(m)$ holds, then we have to prove that

$$C = H_0(d_1, d_2, d_3, d_5, \dots, d_{2^k+1}, \dots, d_{2^{N-1}+1}),$$

and

$$D = H_1(d_1, d_2, d_3, d_5, \dots, d_{2^k+1}, \dots, d_{2^{N-1}+1}).$$

Define the sets

$$C_1 = \{c_1, \dots, c_{2^{N-1}}\}, \quad C_2 = C \setminus C_1,$$

and

$$D_1 = \{d_1, \dots, d_{2^{N-1}}\}, \quad D_2 = D \setminus D_1.$$

We prove that for every positive integer m , we have

$$R_{C_1}(m) = R_{D_1}(m). \tag{3}$$

Since $d_{2^{N-1}} \leq \frac{1}{4}d_{2^{N-1}+1}$, it follows that for any $d_i, d_j \in D_1$ we have

$$d_i + d_j \leq \frac{1}{4}d_{2^{N-1}+1} + \frac{1}{4}d_{2^{N-1}+1} = \frac{1}{2}d_{2^{N-1}+1}.$$

This implies that for every $\frac{1}{2}d_{2^{N-1}+1} \leq m \leq d_{2^{N-1}+1}$, we have $R_D(m) = 0$, which yields $R_C(m) = 0$. As $0 \in C$, we have a representation $m = 0 + m$. It follows that $m \notin C$ for $\frac{1}{2}d_{2^{N-1}+1} \leq m \leq d_{2^{N-1}+1}$. We will show that

$$C_1 = \left[0, \frac{1}{3}d_{2^{N-1}+1}\right[\cap C, \quad D_1 = \left[0, \frac{1}{3}d_{2^{N-1}+1}\right[\cap D.$$

We distinguish two cases. In the first case we assume that $c_{2^{N-1}+1} \leq \frac{d_{2^{N-1}+1}}{2}$. Then we have

$$\binom{2^{N-1}+1}{2} \leq \sum_{m < d_{2^{N-1}+1}} R_C(m) = \sum_{m < d_{2^{N-1}+1}} R_D(m) = \binom{2^{N-1}}{2}$$

which is a contradiction. In the second case we assume that $c_{2^{N-1}} > \frac{d_{2^{N-1}+1}}{2}$, which implies that $c_{2^{N-1}} \geq d_{2^{N-1}+1}$. Then we have

$$\binom{2^{N-1}-1}{2} \geq \sum_{m < d_{2^{N-1}+1}} R_C(m) = \sum_{m < d_{2^{N-1}+1}} R_D(m) = \binom{2^{N-1}}{2},$$

which is impossible. Then we have $c_{2^{N-1}} \leq \frac{1}{2}d_{2^{N-1}+1} < c_{2^{N-1}+1}$ and $d_{2^{N-1}+1} < c_{2^{N-1}+1}$, which implies that

$$R_{C_1}(m) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } m \geq d_{2^{N-1}+1} \\ R_C(m), & \text{if } m < d_{2^{N-1}+1} \end{cases},$$

and

$$R_{D_1}(m) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } m \geq d_{2^{N-1}+1} \\ R_D(m), & \text{if } m < d_{2^{N-1}+1} \end{cases}.$$

It follows that for every positive integer m , $R_{C_1}(m) = R_{D_1}(m)$, which proves (3). By the induction hypothesis we get that

$$C_1 = H_0(d_1, d_2, d_3, d_5, \dots, d_{2^k+1}, \dots, d_{2^{N-2}+1})$$

and

$$D_1 = H_1(d_1, d_2, d_3, d_5, \dots, d_{2^k+1}, \dots, d_{2^{N-2}+1}).$$

By Theorem 4, $d_{2^{k-1}+1} \leq d_{2^k} \leq \frac{1}{4}d_{2^k+1}$ for $1 \leq k \leq N-1$. This implies that $d_{2^{N-i}+1} \leq \frac{1}{4^{i-1}}d_{2^{N-1}+1}$ for $i = 2, \dots, N$ and $d_1 \leq \frac{1}{4^N}d_{2^{N-1}+1}$. It follows that the largest element of the set $H(d_1, d_2, d_3, d_5, d_9, \dots, d_{2^{N-2}+1})$ is

$$\begin{aligned} & d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + d_5 + d_9 + \dots + d_{2^{N-2}+1} \\ & \leq \frac{1}{4^N}d_{2^{N-1}+1} + \frac{1}{4^{N-1}}d_{2^{N-1}+1} + \dots + \frac{1}{4}d_{2^{N-1}+1} < \frac{1}{3}d_{2^{N-1}+1}, \end{aligned}$$

which implies that

$$C_1 = \left[0, \frac{1}{3}d_{2^{N-1}+1} \right[\cap C, \quad D_1 = \left]0, \frac{1}{3}d_{2^{N-1}+1} \right[\cap D. \tag{4}$$

Therefore,

$$C_1 + C_1 \subset \left[0, \frac{2}{3}d_{2^{N-1}+1} \right[, \quad D_1 + D_1 \subset \left[0, \frac{2}{3}d_{2^{N-1}+1} \right[. \tag{5}$$

Furthermore, for every $d \in D_2$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & d_{2^{N-1}+1} \leq d \leq d_{2^N} \leq d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-2}+1} + \dots + d_{2^i+1} + \dots + d_2 + d_1 \\ & \leq d_{2^{N-1}+1} + \frac{1}{4}d_{2^{N-1}+1} + \dots + \frac{1}{4^{N-i-1}}d_{2^{N-1}+1} + \dots \\ & + \frac{1}{4^{N-1}}d_{2^{N-1}+1} + \frac{1}{4^N}d_{2^{N-1}+1} \\ & < \frac{4}{3}d_{2^{N-1}+1}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, we conclude

$$D_1 + D_2 \subset \left[d_{2^{N-1}+1}, \frac{5}{3}d_{2^{N-1}+1} \right], \tag{6}$$

and

$$D_2 + D_2 \subset \left[2d_{2^{N-1}+1}, \frac{8}{3}d_{2^{N-1}+1} \right]. \tag{7}$$

It follows that

$$R_C(m) = 0 \text{ for } m \geq \frac{8}{3}d_{2^{N-1}+1}. \tag{8}$$

We now show that $c_{2^{N-1}+1} = d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_1$. Assume that

$$c_{2^{N-1}+1} < d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_1. \tag{9}$$

Obviously, $c_{2^{N-1}+1} > d_{2^{N-1}+1}$. Since $c_{2^{N-1}+1} = c_{2^{N-1}+1} + 0$, then we have $1 \leq R_C(c_{2^{N-1}+1}) = R_D(c_{2^{N-1}+1})$, which implies that $c_{2^{N-1}+1} = d_i + d_j$, $i < j$, $d_i, d_j \in D$. If $j \leq 2^{N-1}$, then by using the first condition in Theorem 4 we have

$$c_{2^{N-1}+1} = d_i + d_j \leq 2d_{2^{N-1}} \leq \frac{1}{2}d_{2^{N-1}+1},$$

which contradicts the inequality $c_{2^{N-1}+1} \geq d_{2^{N-1}+1}$. Moreover, when $j \geq 2^{N-1} + 1$, we have

$$c_{2^{N-1}+1} = d_i + d_j \geq d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+1},$$

which contradicts (9).

Assume that $c_{2^{N-1}+1} > d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_1$. Obviously, $1 \leq R_D(d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_1) = R_C(d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_1)$, which implies that $d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+1} = c_i + c_j$, $i < j$, $c_i, c_j \in C$. If $j \leq 2^{N-1}$, then we have

$$d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+1} = c_i + c_j \leq 2c_{2^{N-1}} \leq d_{2^{N-1}+1},$$

which is impossible. Moreover, when $j \geq 2^{N-1} + 1$, we have

$$d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+1} = c_i + c_j \geq c_{2^{N-1}+1} > d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_1$$

which is a contradiction.

It follows that for every $c \in C$ with $c > c_{2^{N-1}+1}$, we have $c \leq \frac{5}{3}d_{2^{N-1}+1}$. Otherwise, $c + c_{2^{N-1}+1} \geq \frac{8}{3}d_{2^{N-1}+1}$ and then $R_C(c + c_{2^{N-1}+1}) \geq 1$, which contradicts (8). By (4) and (8) we have

$$C_1 + C_2 \subset \left[d_{2^{N-1}+1}, 2d_{2^{N-1}+1} \right], \tag{10}$$

and

$$(C_2 + C_2) \setminus \{2c_{2^N}\} \subset \left[2d_{2^{N-1}+1}, \frac{8}{3}d_{2^{N-1}+1} \right]. \tag{11}$$

It suffices to prove that

$$C_2 = d_{2^{N-1}+1} + H_1(d_1, d_2, d_3, d_5, \dots, d_{2^{N-2}+1}) = d_{2^{N-1}+1} + D_1,$$

and

$$D_2 = d_{2^{N-1}+1} + H_0(d_1, d_2, d_3, d_5, \dots, d_{2^{N-2}+1}) = d_{2^{N-1}+1} + C_1.$$

Define the sets

$$C_{2,n} = \{c_{2^{N-1}+1}, c_{2^{N-1}+2}, \dots, c_{2^{N-1}+n}\},$$

and

$$D_{2,n} = \{d_{2^{N-1}+1}, d_{2^{N-1}+2}, \dots, d_{2^{N-1}+n}\}.$$

Furthermore, define the sets

$$C_1 + C_{2,n} = \{p_1, p_2, \dots\}, \quad (p_1 < p_2 < \dots),$$

$$C_{2,n} + C_{2,n} = \{t_1, t_2, \dots\}, \quad (t_1 < t_2 < \dots),$$

and

$$D_1 + D_{2,n} = \{q_1, q_2, \dots\}, \quad (q_1 < q_2 < \dots),$$

$$D_{2,n} + D_{2,n} = \{s_1, s_2, \dots\}, \quad (s_1 < s_2 < \dots).$$

Denote the first $2^{N-1} + n$ elements of the set

$$H_0(d_1, d_2, d_3, d_5, \dots, d_{2^k+1}, \dots, d_{2^{N-1}+1})$$

by $H_0^{(n)}$, and let $H_1^{(n)}$ denote the first $2^{N-1} + n$ elements of the set

$$H_1(d_1, d_2, d_3, d_5, \dots, d_{2^k+1}, \dots, d_{2^{N-1}+1}).$$

Now we prove by induction on n that

$$H_0^{(n)} = C_1 \cup C_{2,n} \text{ and } H_1^{(n)} = D_1 \cup D_{2,n}$$

for $1 \leq n \leq 2^{N-1}$. For $n = 1$ we have already proved that $D_{2,1} = \{d_{2^{N-1}+1}\}$ and $C_{2,1} = \{d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_1\}$. It follows that $H_0^{(1)} = C_1 \cup C_{2,1}$ and $H_1^{(1)} = D_1 \cup D_{2,1}$. Let us suppose that $H_0^{(n)} = C_1 \cup C_{2,n}$ and $H_1^{(n)} = D_1 \cup D_{2,n}$ and we are going to prove that $H_0^{(n+1)} = C_1 \cup C_{2,n+1}$ and $H_1^{(n+1)} = D_1 \cup D_{2,n+1}$. To prove $H_0^{(n+1)} = C_1 \cup C_{2,n+1}$ and $H_1^{(n+1)} = D_1 \cup D_{2,n+1}$, we need three lemmas. Let i be the smallest index u such that $r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(p_u) > r_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(p_u)$. If such an i does not exist, then $p_i = +\infty$. Let j be the smallest index v such that $r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(q_v) < r_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(q_v)$. If such a j does not exist, then $q_j = +\infty$. Let k be the smallest index w such that $R_{C_{2,n}}(t_w) > R_{D_{2,n}}(t_w)$. If such a k does not exist, then $t_k = +\infty$. Let l be the smallest index x such that $R_{C_{2,n}}(s_x) < R_{D_{2,n}}(s_x)$. If such an l does not exist, then $s_l = +\infty$. The following observations play a crucial role in the proof.

Lemma 1. *Let us suppose that $H_0^{(n)} = C_1 \cup C_{2,n}$ and $H_1^{(n)} = D_1 \cup D_{2,n}$. Then we have*

- (i) $\min\{p_i, c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}\} = \min\{q_j, d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}\},$
- (ii) $\min\{t_k, c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}\} = \min\{s_l, d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}\}.$

Proof. In the first step we prove (i). We will prove that $p_i = +\infty$ is equivalent to $q_j = +\infty$ and for $p_i = q_j = +\infty$, we have $r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(m) = r_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(m)$. Assume that $p_i = +\infty$. Then by the definition of p_i , we have $r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(p_f) \leq r_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(p_f)$ for every positive integer f . It follows that

$$r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(m) \leq r_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(m)$$

for every positive integer m . On the other hand,

$$2^{N-1} \cdot n = \sum_m r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(m) \leq \sum_m r_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(m) = 2^{N-1} \cdot n.$$

Then $r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(m) = r_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(m)$ for every positive integer m , which implies that $q_j = +\infty$. Suppose that $q_j = +\infty$. Then by the definition of q_j , we have $r_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(q_g) \leq r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(q_g)$ for every positive integer g . It follows that

$$r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(m) \geq r_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(m)$$

for every positive integer m . Moreover,

$$2^{N-1} \cdot n = \sum_m r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(m) \geq \sum_m r_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(m) = 2^{N-1} \cdot n.$$

Then $r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(m) = r_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(m)$ for every positive integer m , which implies that $p_i = +\infty$.

We distinguish two cases.

Case 1. $p_i = +\infty, q_j = +\infty$, that is, $r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(m) = r_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(m)$ for every positive integer m . Now we prove that $c_{2^{N-1}+n+1} = d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}$. Assume that $c_{2^{N-1}+n+1} < d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}$. Since $c_{2^{N-1}+n+1} = 0 + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}$, where $0 \in C_1$ but $c_{2^{N-1}+n+1} \in C_2 \setminus C_{2,n}$ it follows from (5), (6), (7) and (10) that $R_D(c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) = r_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(c_{2^{N-1}+n+1})$ and $R_C(c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) > r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(c_{2^{N-1}+n+1})$. Then we have

$$R_D(c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) = r_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) = r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) < R_C(c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}),$$

which is impossible. Similarly, if $c_{2^{N-1}+n+1} > d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}$, then $R_D(d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) > r_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1})$ because $d_1 \in D_1, d_{2^{N-1}+n+1} \in D_2 \setminus D_{2,n}$. It follows from (5), (6), (10) and (11) that $R_C(d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) = r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1})$. Then we have

$$R_C(d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) = r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) = r_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1})$$

$$< R_D(d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}),$$

which is a contradiction.

Case 2. $p_i < +\infty$ and $q_j < +\infty$. We have two subcases.

Case 2a. $\min\{p_i, c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}\} < \min\{q_j, d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}\}$.

If $p_i \leq c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}$, then obviously $p_i < d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}$, which implies by (5), (6), (7) and (10) that $R_D(p_i) = r_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(p_i)$. By using the above facts and the definition of p_i , we get that

$$R_C(p_i) \geq r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(p_i) > r_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(p_i) = R_D(p_i),$$

which contradicts the fact that $R_C(m) = R_D(m)$ for every positive integer m . On the other hand, if $p_i > c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}$, then by the definition of p_i , $r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) \leq r_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(c_{2^{N-1}+n+1})$. Since $c_{2^{N-1}+n+1} = 0 + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}$, $0 \in C_1$ and $c_{2^{N-1}+n+1} \in C_2 \setminus C_{2,n}$, we have

$$R_C(c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) > r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}). \tag{12}$$

The condition $\min\{p_i, c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}\} < \min\{q_j, d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}\}$ implies that $q_j > c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}$. It follows from the definition of q_j that

$$r_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) \leq r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}).$$

We conclude that

$$r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) = r_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}). \tag{13}$$

It follows from $0 + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1} < d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}$, $0 \in C_1$, (5), (6), (7) and (10) that $r_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) = R_D(c_{2^{N-1}+n+1})$. Furthermore, we obtain from (12) and (13) that

$$R_D(c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) = r_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) = r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) < R_C(c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}),$$

which contradicts the fact that $R_C(m) = R_D(m)$ for every positive integer m .

Case 2b. $\min\{p_i, c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}\} > \min\{q_j, d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}\}$.

If $q_j \leq d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}$, then obviously $q_j < c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}$, which implies from (5), (6), (10) and (11) that $R_C(q_j) = r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(q_j)$. By using the above facts and the definition of q_j , we get that

$$R_C(q_j) = r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(q_j) < r_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(q_j) \leq R_D(q_j),$$

which contradicts the fact that $R_C(m) = R_D(m)$ for every positive integer m .

Moreover, if $q_j > d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}$, then by the definition of q_j ,

$$r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) \geq r_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}).$$

Since $d_1 \in D_1$, $d_{2^{N-1}+n+1} \in D_2 \setminus D_{2,n}$, we have

$$R_D(d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) > r_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}). \tag{14}$$

The assumption $\min\{p_i, c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}\} > \min\{q_j, d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}\}$ implies that $p_i > d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}$. It follows from the definition of p_i that

$$r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) \leq r_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}).$$

We conclude that

$$r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) = r_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}). \tag{15}$$

It follows from $\min\{p_i, c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}\} > \min\{q_j, d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}\}$ that $c_{2^{N-1}+n+1} > d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}$. Therefore, it follows from (5), (6), (10) and (11) that

$$r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) = R_C(d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}). \tag{16}$$

Furthermore, from (14),(15) and (16) we have

$$\begin{aligned} R_D(d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) &> r_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) \\ &= r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) = R_C(d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}), \end{aligned}$$

which contradicts the fact that $R_C(m) = R_D(m)$ for every positive integer m . The proof of (i) in Lemma 1 is completed.

The proof of (ii) in Lemma 1 is similar to the proof of (i). For the sake of completeness, we present it. We prove that $s_l = +\infty$ is equivalent to $t_k = +\infty$ and in this case $R_{C_{2,n}}(m) = R_{D_{2,n}}(m)$ for every positive integer m . If $t_k = +\infty$, then by the definition of t_k , we have $R_{C_{2,n}}(t_f) \leq R_{D_{2,n}}(t_f)$ for every positive integer f . Then

$$R_{C_{2,n}}(m) \leq R_{D_{2,n}}(m)$$

for every positive integer m . On the other hand, we have

$$\binom{n}{2} = \sum_m R_{C_{2,n}}(m) \leq \sum_m R_{D_{2,n}}(m) = \binom{n}{2}.$$

It follows that $R_{C_{2,n}}(m) = R_{D_{2,n}}(m)$ for every positive integer m , which implies that $s_l = +\infty$. If $s_l = +\infty$, then by the definition of s_l , we have $R_{C_{2,n}}(s_g) \geq R_{D_{2,n}}(s_g)$ for every positive integer g . Then

$$R_{C_{2,n}}(m) \geq R_{D_{2,n}}(m)$$

for every positive integer m . Furthermore,

$$\binom{n}{2} = \sum_m R_{C_{2,n}}(m) \geq \sum_m R_{D_{2,n}}(m) = \binom{n}{2}.$$

Then, we have $R_{C_{2,n}}(m) = R_{D_{2,n}}(m)$ for every positive integer m , which implies that $t_k = +\infty$. We distinguish two cases.

Case 1. $t_k = +\infty$, $s_l = +\infty$, that is, $R_{C_{2,n}}(m) = R_{D_{2,n}}(m)$ for every positive integer m . Now, we prove that $d_{2^{N-1}+n+1} = d_1 + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}$. Assume that $d_{2^{N-1}+n+1} > d_1 + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}$. As $d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1} = c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}$, where $c_{2^{N-1}+1} \in C_{2,n}$ and $c_{2^{N-1}+n+1} \in C_2 \setminus C_{2,n}$, it follows that

$$R_C(c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) > R_{C_{2,n}}(c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}).$$

On the other hand, we will show that

$$d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1} > d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1} = c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}$$

and (5), (6), (7), (11) imply

$$R_D(c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) = R_{D_{2,n}}(c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}).$$

It is clear from (11) that

$$c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1} \in (C_2 + C_2) \setminus \{2c_{2^N}\} \subset \left[2d_{2^{N-1}+1}, \frac{8}{3}d_{2^{N-1}+1} \right].$$

By (5) and (6), we have $c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1} \notin (D_1 + D_1) \cup (D_1 + D_2)$. This implies that $R_D(c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) = R_{D_2}(c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1})$. Moreover, $D_2 = D_{2,n} \cup (D_2 \setminus D_{2,n})$, thus we have

$$R_{D_2}(m) = R_{D_{2,n}}(m) + 2r_{D_2+(D_2 \setminus D_{2,n})}(m) + R_{D_2 \setminus D_{2,n}}(m)$$

for any positive integer m . We conclude that for any positive integer m with $2d_{2^{N-1}+1} \leq m < d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}$, we have $r_{D_2+(D_2 \setminus D_{2,n})}(m) = 0$ and

$$R_{D_2 \setminus D_{2,n}}(m) = 0.$$

This implies that $R_{D_2}(m) = R_{D_{2,n}}(m)$, and then

$$R_D(c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) = R_{D_{2,n}}(c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}).$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} R_D(c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) &= R_{D_{2,n}}(c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) \\ &= R_{C_{2,n}}(c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) < R_C(c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}), \end{aligned}$$

which is impossible. Similarly, if $d_1 + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1} > d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}$, then it follows that $R_D(d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) > R_{D_{2,n}}(d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1})$ because $d_{2^{N-1}+1} \in D_{2,n}$ and $d_{2^{N-1}+n+1} \in D_2 \setminus D_{2,n}$. It follows from (5), (7), (10), (11) and

$$d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1} < d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1} = c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}$$

that $R_{C_{2,n}}(d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) = R_C(d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1})$. Then, we have

$$\begin{aligned} R_C(d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) &= R_{C_{2,n}}(d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) \\ &= R_{D_{2,n}}(d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) < R_D(d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}), \end{aligned}$$

which is a contradiction.

Case 2. $t_k < +\infty$ and $s_l < +\infty$. We have two subcases.

Case 2a. $\min\{t_k, c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}\} < \min\{s_l, d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}\}$. If $t_k \leq c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}$, then obviously $t_k < d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}$. By using (5), (6), (7), (11) we have $R_D(t_k) = R_{D_{2,n}}(t_k)$. By the definition of t_k , we get that

$$R_C(t_k) \geq R_{C_{2,n}}(t_k) > R_{D_{2,n}}(t_k) = R_D(t_k),$$

which contradicts the fact that $R_C(t_k) = R_D(t_k)$.

On the other hand, if $t_k > c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}$, then by the definition of t_k , we have $R_{C_{2,n}}(c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) \leq R_{D_{2,n}}(c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1})$. Moreover, it follows from $c_{2^{N-1}+1} \in C_{2,n}$ and $c_{2^{N-1}+n+1} \in C_2 \setminus C_{2,n}$ that

$$R_C(c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) > R_{C_{2,n}}(c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}).$$

Since $\min\{t_k, c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}\} < \min\{s_l, d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}\}$, we have $c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1} < s_l$. By the definition of s_l , $R_{D_{2,n}}(c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) \leq R_{C_{2,n}}(c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1})$. Then, we have

$$R_{C_{2,n}}(c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) = R_{D_{2,n}}(c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}).$$

By

$$\begin{aligned} c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1} &= \min\{t_k, c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}\} \\ &< \min\{s_l, d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}\} \leq d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1} \end{aligned}$$

and (5), (6), (7), (11), we have

$$R_{D_{2,n}}(c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) = R_D(c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}),$$

and then

$$\begin{aligned} R_D(c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) &= R_{D_{2,n}}(c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) \\ &= R_{C_{2,n}}(c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) < R_C(c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}), \end{aligned}$$

which contradicts the fact that

$$R_C(c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) = R_D(c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}).$$

Case 2b. $\min\{t_k, c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}\} > \min\{s_l, d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}\}$.

If $s_l \leq d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}$, then obviously $s_l < c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}$. By the definition of s_l and (5), (7), (10), (11), it follows that $R_{C_{2,n}}(s_l) = R_C(s_l)$, and then

$$R_C(s_l) = R_{C_{2,n}}(s_l) < R_{D_{2,n}}(s_l) \leq R_D(s_l),$$

which contradicts the fact that $R_C(s_l) = R_D(s_l)$. On the other hand, if $s_l > d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}$, then by the definition of s_l , $R_{C_{2,n}}(d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) \geq R_{D_{2,n}}(d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1})$. Since $d_{2^{N-1}+1} \in D_2$, $d_{2^{N-1}+n+1} \in D_2 \setminus D_{2,n}$, we have

$$R_D(d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) > R_{D_{2,n}}(d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}).$$

It follows from $\min\{t_k, c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}\} > \min\{s_l, d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}\}$ that $t_k > d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}$. By the definition of t_k ,

$$R_{C_{2,n}}(d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) \leq R_{D_{2,n}}(d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}),$$

and then $R_{C_{2,n}}(d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) = R_{D_{2,n}}(d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1})$. By

$$d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1} < c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}$$

and (5), (7), (10), (11), we have

$$R_{C_{2,n}}(d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) = R_C(d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}),$$

and then

$$\begin{aligned} R_C(d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) &= R_{C_{2,n}}(d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) \\ &= R_{D_{2,n}}(d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) < R_D(d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}), \end{aligned}$$

which contradicts the fact that

$$R_C(d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}) = R_D(d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}).$$

The proof of (ii) in Lemma 1 is completed. □

Let

$$H = H(d_1, d_2, d_3, d_5, \dots, d_{2^k+1}, \dots, d_{2^{N-1}+1})$$

and

$$H_0 = H_0(d_1, d_2, d_3, d_5, \dots, d_{2^k+1}, \dots, d_{2^{N-1}+1})$$

$$H_1 = H_1(d_1, d_2, d_3, d_5, \dots, d_{2^k+1}, \dots, d_{2^{N-1}+1}).$$

If $R_{H_0}(m) > 0$ or $R_{H_1}(m) > 0$, then

$$m = \delta_0 d_1 + \sum_{i=1}^N \delta_i d_{2^{i-1}+1},$$

where $\delta_0, \delta_i \in \{0, 1, 2\}$. It follows from $d_2 \geq 4d_1, d_{2^{k+1}} \geq 4d_{2^{k-1}+1}, (k = 1, \dots, N-1)$ that when

$$m' = \delta'_0 d_1 + \sum_{i=1}^N \delta'_i d_{2^{i-1}+1},$$

where $\delta'_0, \delta'_i \in \{0, 1, 2\}$ and $(\delta_0, \dots, \delta_N) \neq (\delta'_0, \dots, \delta'_N)$, then $m \neq m'$. On the other hand, if

$$m = \delta_0 d_1 + \sum_{i=1}^N \delta_i d_{2^{i-1}+1},$$

where $\delta_0, \delta_i \in \{0, 1, 2\}$, then $m = k + k'$ with

$$k = \varepsilon_0 d_1 + \sum_{i=1}^N \varepsilon_i d_{2^{i-1}+1},$$

where $\varepsilon_0, \varepsilon_i \in \{0, 1\}$ and

$$k' = \varepsilon'_0 d_1 + \sum_{i=1}^N \varepsilon'_i d_{2^{i-1}+1},$$

where $\varepsilon'_0, \varepsilon'_i \in \{0, 1\}$ if and only if $\delta_0 = \varepsilon_0 + \varepsilon'_0$ and $\delta_i = \varepsilon_i + \varepsilon'_i, 1 \leq i \leq N$.

Let $H_{0,n}$ and $H_{1,n}$ denote the $2^{N-1} + n$ th elements of H_0 and H_1 , respectively. If

$$H_{0,n} = \varepsilon_0 d_1 + \sum_{i=1}^N \varepsilon_i d_{2^{i-1}+1},$$

where $\varepsilon_0, \varepsilon_i \in \{0, 1\}$, then it follows from $d_2 \geq 4d_1$ and $d_{2^{k+1}} \geq 4d_{2^{k-1}+1}, (k = 1, \dots, N-1)$ that

$$H_{1,n} = (1 - \varepsilon_0) d_1 + \sum_{i=1}^N \varepsilon_i d_{2^{i-1}+1}.$$

In the next step, we prove the following lemma.

Lemma 2. *Let us suppose that $H_0^{(n)} = C_1 \cup C_{2,n}$ and $H_1^{(n)} = D_1 \cup D_{2,n}$ holds for some $1 \leq n < 2^{N-1}$. Let $H_{0,n+1} = \varepsilon_0 d_1 + \sum_{i=1}^N \varepsilon_i d_{2^{i-1}+1}$. If $\varepsilon_0 = 0$ and $H_{0,n+1} = d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1}$, where $1 \leq i_1 < i_2 < \dots < i_t < N$, then we have*

(i) $q_j = H_{0,n+1}$,

(ii) $p_i > q_j$.

If $t > 1$, then

(iii) $s_l = 2d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + 2d_{2^{N-1}+1}$,

(iv) $t_k > s_l$.

If $t = 1$, then

(v) $t_k = s_l = +\infty$.

Proof. We prove (i) and (ii) simultaneously. It is enough to show that if $m < H_{0,n+1}$, then $r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(m) = r_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(m)$ and $r_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(H_{0,n+1}) > r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(H_{0,n+1})$. If $m < d_{2^{N-1}+1}$, then it follows from (6) and (10) that $r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(m) = r_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(m) = 0$. If $d_{2^{N-1}+1} \leq m < H_{0,n+1}$, then by using (5), (7), (11) and $H_{1,n+1} = H_{0,n+1} + d_1$, it follows that $R_{H_0}(m) = r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(m)$ and $R_{H_1}(m) = r_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(m)$. It follows from $R_{H_0}(m) = R_{H_1}(m)$ that $r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(m) = r_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(m)$. By using (5), (7), (11) and $H_{0,n+1} < H_{1,n+1}$, we get that $R_{H_1}(H_{0,n+1}) = r_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(H_{0,n+1})$. Since $H_{0,n+1} = 0 + H_{0,n+1}$, where $0, H_{0,n+1} \in H_0$ and $H_{0,n+1} \notin C_{2,n}$, we have $R_{H_0}(H_{0,n+1}) > r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(H_{0,n+1})$. It follows from $R_{H_0}(H_{0,n+1}) = R_{H_1}(H_{0,n+1})$ that $r_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(H_{0,n+1}) > r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(H_{0,n+1})$, which proves (i) and (ii).

We prove (iii) and (iv) simultaneously. Let

$$M = 2d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + 2d_{2^{N-1}+1}.$$

It is enough to show that if $m < M$, then $R_{C_{2,n}}(m) = R_{D_{2,n}}(m)$ and $R_{C_{2,n}}(M) < R_{D_{2,n}}(M)$. If $m < 2d_{2^{N-1}+1}$, then by using (7) and (11), we have $R_{C_{2,n}}(m) = R_{D_{2,n}}(m) = 0$. Let

$$2d_{2^{N-1}+1} \leq m < d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + 2d_{2^{N-1}+1},$$

and write $m = h + h'$ with $h, h' \in H_0$. By using (5) and (10), we get that $h, h' \in H_0 \setminus C_1$. Since $h \geq d_{2^{N-1}+1}$, we have

$$h' < d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1} = H_{0,n+1},$$

thus $h, h' \in C_{2,n}$, which yields $R_{H_0}(m) = R_{C_{2,n}}(m)$. On the other hand, write $m = h + h'$ with $h, h' \in H_1$. By using (5) and (6), we get that $h, h' \in H_1 \setminus D_1$. Since $h \geq d_{2^{N-1}+1}$, we have

$$h' < d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1} = H_{0,n+1} < H_{1,n+1},$$

thus $h, h' \in D_{2,n}$, which yields $R_{H_1}(m) = R_{D_{2,n}}(m)$. It follows from $R_{H_0}(m) = R_{H_1}(m)$ that $R_{C_{2,n}}(m) = R_{D_{2,n}}(m)$. Suppose that

$$\begin{aligned} & d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + 2d_{2^{N-1}+1} \\ & \leq m < 2d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + 2d_{2^{N-1}+1}. \end{aligned}$$

We can assume that

$$m = \delta_0 d_1 + \sum_{i=1}^u d_{2^{x_i-1}+1} + \sum_{i=1}^v 2d_{2^{y_i-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + 2d_{2^{N-1}+1},$$

where $\delta_0 \in \{0, 1, 2\}$ and $1 \leq x_1 < x_2 < \dots < x_u < i_1$ and $1 \leq y_1 < y_2 < \dots < y_v < i_1$ and $x_\alpha \neq y_\beta$ are integers; otherwise, $R_{C_{2,n}}(m) = R_{D_{2,n}}(m) = 0$. Since $H_{0,n+1} = d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1}$, then t is odd, thus we can assume that $\delta_0 + u + t$ is even; otherwise, $R_{C_{2,n}}(m) = R_{D_{2,n}}(m) = 0$. We distinguish three cases.

Case 1. $\delta_0 = 0$. Then, u is odd. If $m = h + h'$ with $h < h'$ and $h, h' \in H_0$, then it follows from (5) and (10) that $h, h' \in H_0 \setminus C_1$. It is clear that $h' \notin C_{2,n}$ if and only if

$$h' = \sum_{j=1}^w d_{2^{z_j-1}+1} + \sum_{j=1}^v d_{2^{y_j-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1},$$

where $\{z_1, \dots, z_w\} \subset \{x_1, \dots, x_u\} \neq \emptyset$ and $w + v + t + 1$ is even. There are 2^{u-1} ways to choose the set $\{z_1, \dots, z_w\}$, thus we have $R_{C_{2,n}}(m) = R_{H_0}(m) - 2^{u-1}$.

Furthermore, if $m = h + h'$ with $h < h'$ and $h, h' \in H_1$, then it follows from (5) and (6) that $h, h' \in H_0 \setminus D_1$. It is clear that $h' \notin D_{2,n}$ if and only if

$$h' = \sum_{j=1}^w d_{2^{z_j-1}+1} + \sum_{j=1}^v d_{2^{y_j-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1},$$

where $\{z_1, \dots, z_w\} \subset \{x_1, \dots, x_u\} \neq \emptyset$ and $w + v + t + 1$ is odd. There are 2^{u-1} ways to choose the set $\{z_1, \dots, z_w\}$, thus we have $R_{C_{2,n}}(m) = R_{H_1}(m) - 2^{u-1}$. As $R_{H_0}(m) = R_{H_1}(m)$, it follows that $R_{C_{2,n}}(m) = R_{D_{2,n}}(m)$.

Case 2. $\delta_0 = 1$. Then, u is even. If $m = h + h'$ with $h < h'$ and $h, h' \in H_0$, then it follows from (5) and (10) that $h, h' \in H_0 \setminus C_1$. It is clear that $h' \notin C_{2,n}$ if and only if

$$h' = \varepsilon_0 d_1 + \sum_{j=1}^w d_{2^{z_j-1}+1} + \sum_{j=1}^v d_{2^{y_j-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1},$$

where $\varepsilon_0 \in \{0, 1\}$ and $\{z_1, \dots, z_w\} \subset \{x_1, \dots, x_u\}$ and $\varepsilon_0 + w + v + t + 1$ is even. If $u = 0$, then for a suitable ε_0 , there is only one possibility for h' , thus we have $R_{C_{2,n}}(m) = R_{H_0}(m) - 1$. If $u > 0$, to choose the pairs $(\varepsilon_0, \{z_1, \dots, z_w\})$, we have $2 \cdot 2^{u-1} = 2^u$ possibilities, thus we have $R_{C_{2,n}}(m) = R_{H_0}(m) - 2^u$. Moreover, if $m = h + h'$, with $h < h'$ and $h, h' \in H_1$, then it follows from (5) and (6) that $h, h' \in H_1 \setminus D_1$. It is clear that $h' \notin D_{2,n}$ if and only if

$$h' = \varepsilon_0 d_1 + \sum_{j=1}^w d_{2^{z_j-1}+1} + \sum_{j=1}^v d_{2^{y_j-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1},$$

where $\varepsilon_0 \in \{0, 1\}$ and $\{z_1, \dots, z_w\} \subset \{x_1, \dots, x_u\}$ and $\varepsilon_0 + w + v + t + 1$ is odd. If $u = 0$, then for a suitable ε_0 , there is only one possibility for h' thus we have $R_{D_{2,n}}(m) = R_{H_1}(m) - 1$. When $u > 0$, to choose the pairs $(\varepsilon_0, \{z_1, \dots, z_w\})$,

we have $2 \cdot 2^{u-1} = 2^u$ possibilities, thus we have $R_{D_{2,n}}(m) = R_{H_1}(m) - 2^u$. As $R_{H_0}(m) = R_{H_1}(m)$, it follows that $R_{C_{2,n}}(m) = R_{D_{2,n}}(m)$.

Case 3. $\delta_0 = 2$. Then, u is odd. If $m = h + h'$ with $h < h'$ and $h, h' \in H_0$, then it follows from (5) and (10) that $h, h' \in H_0 \setminus C_1$. It is clear that $h' \notin C_{2,n}$ if and only if

$$h' = d_1 + \sum_{j=1}^w d_{2^{z_j-1}+1} + \sum_{j=1}^v d_{2^{y_j-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1},$$

where $\{z_1, \dots, z_w\} \subset \{x_1, \dots, x_u\} \neq \emptyset$ and $1 + w + v + t + 1$ is even. There are 2^{u-1} ways to choose the set $\{z_1, \dots, z_w\}$, thus we have $R_{C_{2,n}}(m) = R_{H_0}(m) - 2^{u-1}$.

On the other hand, if $m = h + h'$ with $h < h'$ and $h, h' \in H_1$, then it follows from (5) and (6) that $h, h' \in H_0 \setminus D_1$. It is clear that $h' \notin D_{2,n}$ if and only if

$$h' = d_1 + \sum_{j=1}^w d_{2^{z_j-1}+1} + \sum_{j=1}^v d_{2^{y_j-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1},$$

where $\{z_1, \dots, z_w\} \subset \{x_1, \dots, x_u\} \neq \emptyset$ and $1 + w + v + t + 1$ is odd. There are 2^{u-1} ways to choose the set $\{z_1, \dots, z_w\}$, thus we have $R_{C_{2,n}}(m) = R_{H_1}(m) - 2^{u-1}$. As $R_{H_0}(m) = R_{H_1}(m)$, it follows that $R_{C_{2,n}}(m) = R_{D_{2,n}}(m)$. Let

$$M = 2d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + 2d_{2^{N-1}+1}.$$

Now, we prove $R_{D_{2,n}}(M) = R_{H_1}(M)$. Assume that

$$M = 2d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + 2d_{2^{N-1}+1} = h + h',$$

where $h, h' \in H_1$ with $h < h'$. Then, it follows from (5) and (6) that $h, h' \in H_1 \setminus D_1$. It follows that

$$h' = d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{z_1-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{z_w-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1},$$

where $\{z_1, \dots, z_w\} \subset \{i_2, \dots, i_t\}$. Thus, we have

$$h' \leq d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1} = H_{0,n+1} < H_{1,n+1},$$

which implies that $R_{D_{2,n}}(M) = R_{H_1}(M)$. On the other hand,

$$M = (d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1}) + (d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1}),$$

where $d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1} \in C_{2,n}$ and

$$d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1} \notin C_{2,n},$$

and we have

$$d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1} < d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1}$$

because $t \geq 2$. This gives $R_{H_0}(M) > R_{C_{2,n}}(M)$. It follows from $R_{H_0}(M) = R_{H_1}(M)$ that $R_{D_{2,n}}(M) > R_{C_{2,n}}(M)$. Assume that $t = 1$, that is, $H_{0,n+1} = d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1}$. The previous argument shows that for $m < 2d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + 2d_{2^{N-1}+1}$, we have $R_{C_{2,n}}(m) = R_{D_{2,n}}(m)$. Moreover, if $m \geq 2d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + 2d_{2^{N-1}+1} = 2H_{0,n+1}$ and $R_{C_{2,n}}(m) \neq 0$ or $R_{D_{2,n}}(m) \neq 0$, then

$$m = \delta_0 d_1 + \sum_{u=1}^s \delta_u d_{2^{j_u-1}+1} + 2d_{2^{N-1}+1},$$

where $\delta_0 \in \{0, 1, 2\}$, $\delta_u \in \{1, 2\}$, $1 \leq j_1 < j_2 < \dots < j_s < N$ and $j_s \geq i_1$. If $m = h + h'$ with $h, h' \in H_0$ or $h, h' \in H_1$, $h < h'$, then

$$h' = \varepsilon_0 d_1 + \sum_{l=1}^r d_{2^{h_l-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1},$$

where $1 \leq h_1 < j_2 < \dots < h_r$ and $h_r = j_s \geq i_1$. Hence, we have $h' \geq H_{0,n+1}$. It follows that $h' \notin C_{2,n}$ and $h' \notin D_{2,n}$, which implies that $R_{C_{2,n}}(m) = R_{D_{2,n}}(m) = 0$. This proves $s_l = t_k = +\infty$. □

Lemma 3. For $1 \leq n < 2^{N-1}$, let $H_0^{(n)} = C_1 \cup C_{2,n}$ and $H_1^{(n)} = D_1 \cup D_{2,n}$. Let $H_{0,n+1} = \varepsilon_0 d_1 + \sum_{i=1}^N \varepsilon_i d_{2^{i-1}+1}$. If $\varepsilon_0 = 1$ and $H_{0,n+1} = d_1 + d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1}$, where $1 \leq i_1 < i_2 < \dots < i_t < N$, then we have

- (i) $p_i = 2d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1}$,
- (ii) $q_j > p_i$,
- (iii) $t_k = d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + 2d_{2^{N-1}+1}$,
- (iv) $s_l > t_k$.

Proof. We prove (i) and (ii) simultaneously. It is enough to show that for $\varepsilon_0 = 1$ and

$$H_{0,n+1} = d_1 + d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1},$$

if $m < 2d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1}$, then $r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(m) = r_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(m)$ and $r_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(K) < r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(K)$, where

$$K = 2d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1}.$$

If $m < d_{2^{N-1}+1}$, then it follows from (6) and (10) that $r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(m) = r_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(m) = 0$. Assume that

$$d_{2^{N-1}+1} \leq m < d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1}.$$

If $m = h + h'$ with $h < h'$ and $h, h' \in H_0$, then it follows from (5) and (11) that $h \in C_1$ and $h' \in H_0 \setminus C_1$. Since

$$h' < d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1} < H_{0,n+1},$$

we have $h' \in C_{2,n}$, which yields $R_{H_0}(m) = r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(m)$. Upon writing $m = h + h'$ with $h < h'$ and $h, h' \in H_1$, it follows from (5) and (7) that $h \in D_1$ and $h' \in H_1 \setminus D_1$. Since

$$h' < d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1} = H_{1,n+1},$$

we have $h' \in D_{2,n}$. As $R_{H_0}(m) = R_{H_1}(m)$, we have $r_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(m) = r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(m)$. Suppose that

$$\begin{aligned} & d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1} \\ & \leq m < 2d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1}. \end{aligned}$$

Then, we may assume that m can be written in the form

$$m = \delta_0 d_1 + \sum_{i=1}^u d_{2^{x_i-1}+1} + \sum_{i=1}^v 2d_{2^{y_i-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1},$$

where $\delta_0 \in \{0, 1, 2\}$ and $1 \leq x_1 < x_2 < \dots < x_u < i_1$ and $1 \leq y_1 < y_2 < \dots < y_v < i_1$, and $x_\alpha \neq y_\beta$ are integers; otherwise, $r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(m) = r_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(m) = 0$.

Since $H_{0,n+1} = d_1 + d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1}$, we have t is even, thus $\delta_0 + u + 2v + t + 1$ is even, which implies that $\delta_0 + u$ is odd. We distinguish three cases.

Case 1. $\delta_0 = 0$. Then, u is odd. If $m = h + h'$ with $h < h'$ and $h, h' \in H_0$, then it follows from (5) and (10) that $h \in C_1$ and $h' \in H_0 \setminus C_1$. It is clear that $h' \notin C_{2,n}$ if and only if h' can be written in the form

$$h' = \sum_{j=1}^w d_{2^{z_j-1}+1} + \sum_{j=1}^v d_{2^{y_j-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1},$$

where $\{z_1, \dots, z_w\} \subset \{x_1, \dots, x_u\} \neq \emptyset$ and $w + v + t + 1$ is even. There are 2^{u-1} ways to choose the set $\{z_1, \dots, z_w\}$, thus we have $r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(m) = R_{H_0}(m) - 2^{u-1}$. Furthermore, if $m = h + h'$ with $h < h'$ and $h, h' \in H_1$, then it follows from (5) and (7) that $h \in D_1$ and $h' \in H_1 \setminus D_1$. It is clear that $h' \notin D_{2,n}$ if and only if h' can be written in the form

$$h' = \sum_{j=1}^w d_{2^{z_j-1}+1} + \sum_{j=1}^v d_{2^{y_j-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1},$$

where $\{z_1, \dots, z_w\} \subset \{x_1, \dots, x_u\} \neq \emptyset$ and $w + v + t + 1$ is odd. There are 2^{u-1} ways to choose the set $\{z_1, \dots, z_w\}$, thus we have $r_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(m) = R_{H_1}(m) - 2^{u-1}$. As $R_{H_0}(m) = R_{H_1}(m)$, it follows that $r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(m) = r_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(m)$.

Case 2. $\delta_0 = 1$. Then, $1 + u + 2v + t + 1$ is even, which implies that u is even.

If $m = h + h'$ with $h < h'$ and $h, h' \in H_0$, then $h \in C_1$ and $h' \in H_0 \setminus C_1$. It is clear that $h' \notin C_{2,n}$ if and only if h' can be written in the form

$$h' = \varepsilon_0 d_1 + \sum_{j=1}^w d_{2^{z_j-1}+1} + \sum_{j=1}^v d_{2^{y_j-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1},$$

where $\varepsilon_0 \in \{0, 1\}$ and $\{z_1, \dots, z_w\} \subset \{x_1, \dots, x_u\}$ and $\varepsilon_0 + w + v + t + 1$ is even. If $u = 0$, then $\{z_1, \dots, z_w\} = \emptyset$ and for a suitable ε_0 , there is only one way to choose h' , and so $r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(m) = R_{H_0}(m) - 1$. When $u > 0$ is even, to choose the pairs $(\varepsilon_0, \{z_1, \dots, z_w\})$ we have $2 \cdot 2^{u-1} = 2^u$ possibilities, thus we have $r_{C_{2,n}}(m) = R_{H_0}(m) - 2^u$.

On the other hand, if $m = h + h'$ with $h < h'$ and $h, h' \in H_0$, then $h \in D_1$ and $h' \in H_1 \setminus D_1$. It is clear that $h' \notin D_{2,n}$ if and only if h' can be written in the form

$$h' = \varepsilon_0 d_1 + \sum_{j=1}^w d_{2^{z_j-1}+1} + \sum_{j=1}^v d_{2^{y_j-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1},$$

where $\varepsilon_0 \in \{0, 1\}$ and $\{z_1, \dots, z_w\} \subset \{x_1, \dots, x_u\}$ and $\varepsilon_0 + w + v + t + 1$ is odd. If $u = 0$, then $\{z_1, \dots, z_w\} = \emptyset$, and for a suitable ε_0 , there is only one way to choose h' , and so $r_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(m) = R_{H_1}(m) - 1$. For $u > 0$ even, to choose the pairs $(\varepsilon_0, \{z_1, \dots, z_w\})$ we have $2 \cdot 2^{u-1} = 2^u$ possibilities, thus we have $r_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(m) = R_{H_1}(m) - 2^u$. As $R_{H_0}(m) = R_{H_1}(m)$, it follows that $r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(m) = r_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(m)$.

Case 3. $\delta_0 = 2$. Then, $2 + u + 2v + t + 1$ is even, thus u is odd. If $m = h + h'$ with $h < h'$ and $h, h' \in H_0$, then $h \in C_1$ and $h' \in H_0 \setminus C_1$. It is clear that $h' \notin C_{2,n}$ if and only if h' can be written in the form

$$h' = d_1 + \sum_{j=1}^w d_{2^{z_j-1}+1} + \sum_{j=1}^v d_{2^{y_j-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1},$$

where $\{z_1, \dots, z_w\} \subset \{x_1, \dots, x_u\} \neq \emptyset$ and $1 + w + v + t + 1$ is even. There are 2^{u-1} ways to choose the set $\{z_1, \dots, z_w\}$, thus we have $r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(m) = R_{H_0}(m) - 2^{u-1}$. Moreover, if $m = h + h'$ with $h < h'$ and $h, h' \in H_1$, then $h \in D_1$, $h' \in H_1 \setminus D_1$. It is clear that $h' \notin D_{2,n}$ if and only if h' can be written in the form

$$h' = d_1 + \sum_{j=1}^w d_{2^{z_j-1}+1} + \sum_{j=1}^v d_{2^{y_j-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1},$$

where $\{z_1, \dots, z_w\} \subset \{x_1, \dots, x_u\} \neq \emptyset$ and $1 + w + v + t + 1$ is odd. There are 2^{u-1} ways to choose the set $\{z_1, \dots, z_w\}$, thus we have $R_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(m) = R_{H_1}(m) - 2^{u-1}$. As $R_{H_0}(m) = R_{H_1}(m)$, it follows that $r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(m) = r_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(m)$. If

$$K = 2d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1} = h + h'$$

with $h < h'$ and $h, h' \in H_0$, then it follows from (5) and (10) that $h \in C_1$, $h' \in H_0 \setminus C_1$ and h' can be written in the form

$$h' = d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + \sum_{j=1}^w d_{2^{z_j-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1},$$

where $\{z_1, \dots, z_w\} \subset \{i_2, \dots, i_t\} \neq \emptyset$. Thus, we have

$$\begin{aligned} h' &\leq d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1} \\ &< d_1 + d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1} = H_{0,n+1}, \end{aligned}$$

which implies $h' \in C_{2,n}$ and $R_{H_0}(K) = r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(K)$. In the last step, we prove $r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(K) > r_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(K)$. It is clear that

$$K = d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + (d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1}) = d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + H_{1,n+1},$$

where $d_{2^{i_1-1}+1}, H_{1,n+1} \in H_1$. Since $H_{1,n+1} \notin D_{2,n}$, we have $R_{H_1}(K) > r_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(K)$. It follows from $R_{H_0}(K) = R_{H_1}(K)$ that $r_{D_1+D_{2,n}}(K) < r_{C_1+C_{2,n}}(K)$.

We will prove (iii) and (iv) simultaneously. Let

$$L = d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + 2d_{2^{N-1}+1}.$$

We have to prove that if $m < L$, then $R_{D_{2,n}}(m) = R_{C_{2,n}}(m)$ and $R_{D_{2,n}}(L) < R_{C_{2,n}}(L)$. If $m < 2d_{2^{N-1}+1}$, then by using (7) and (11), we get that $R_{D_{2,n}}(m) = R_{C_{2,n}}(m) = 0$. Assume that

$$2d_{2^{N-1}+1} \leq m < L = d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + 2d_{2^{N-1}+1}.$$

If $m = h + h'$ with $h < h'$ and $h, h' \in H_0$, then it follows from (5) and (10) that $h, h' \in H_0 \setminus C_1$. This implies that $h \geq d_{2^{N-1}+1}$ and

$$h' < d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1} < H_{0,n+1}.$$

It follows that $h, h' \in C_{2,n}$, which yields $R_{H_0}(m) = R_{C_{2,n}}(m)$. If $m = h + h'$ with $h < h'$ and $h, h' \in H_1$, then it follows from (5) and (6) that $h, h' \in H_1 \setminus D_1$. Since $h \geq d_{2^{N-1}+1}$ and

$$h' < d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1} = H_{1,n+1},$$

it follows that $h, h' \in D_{2,n}$, which yields $R_{H_1}(m) = R_{D_{2,n}}(m)$. As $R_{H_0}(m) = R_{H_1}(m)$, it follows that $R_{C_{2,n}}(m) = R_{D_{2,n}}(m)$. If

$$L = d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + 2d_{2^{N-1}+1} = h + h'$$

with $h < h'$ and $h, h' \in H_0$, then it follows from (5) and (10) that $h, h' \in H_0 \setminus C_1$. It follows that $h > d_{2^{N-1}+1}$ and

$$h' < d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}} < H_{0,n+1},$$

thus we have $h, h' \in C_{2,n}$, which implies that $R_{H_0}(L) = R_{C_{2,n}}(L)$. On the other hand,

$$\begin{aligned} L &= d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + 2d_{2^{N-1}+1} \\ &= d_{2^{N-1}+1} + (d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1}) \\ &= d_{2^{N-1}+1} + H_{1,n+1}. \end{aligned}$$

Note that $H_{1,n+1}, d_{2^{N-1}+1} \in H_1$ and $H_{1,n+1} \notin D_{2,n}$, which gives $R_{H_1}(L) > R_{C_{2,n}}(L)$. It follows from $R_{H_0}(L) = R_{H_1}(L)$ that $R_{D_{2,n}}(L) > R_{C_{2,n}}(L)$. $\square$

Now we are ready to prove that $H_0^{(n)} = C_1 \cup C_{2,n}$ and $H_1^{(n)} = D_1 \cup D_{2,n}$ hold for every $1 \leq n \leq 2^{N-1}$. We prove by induction on n that $C_1 \cup C_{2,n} = H_0^{(n)}$ and $D_1 \cup D_{2,n} = H_1^{(n)}$. We have already proved $C_1 \cup C_{2,1} = H_0^{(1)}$ and $D_1 \cup D_{2,1} = H_1^{(1)}$. Assume that $C_1 \cup C_{2,n} = H_0^{(n)}$ and $D_1 \cup D_{2,n} = H_1^{(n)}$ hold for some $1 \leq n < 2^{N-1}$. We will prove that $C_1 \cup C_{2,n+1} = H_0^{(n+1)}$ and $D_1 \cup D_{2,n+1} = H_1^{(n+1)}$ hold, i.e., $c_{2^{N-1}+n+1} = H_{0,n+1}$ and $d_{2^{N-1}+n+1} = H_{1,n+1}$. Let

$$H_{0,n+1} = \varepsilon_0 d_1 + \sum_{j=1}^t d_{2^{i_j-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1},$$

where $\varepsilon_0 \in \{0, 1\}$, $(1 \leq i_1 < \dots < i_t < N)$.

Case 1. $\varepsilon_0 = 0, t = 1$. We know from Lemma 1 that

$$\min\{t_k, c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}\} = \min\{s_l, d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}\}$$

and from Lemma 2 that $t_k = s_l = +\infty$. These facts imply that $c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1} = d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}$. Furthermore, we know that $c_{2^{N-1}+1} = d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_1$, thus we have $c_{2^{N-1}+n+1} + d_1 = d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}$, and then $d_{2^{N-1}+n+1} > c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}$. It follows from Lemma 1 that $\min\{p_i, c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}\} = \min\{q_j, d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}\}$ and from Lemma 2 that $p_i > q_j = H_{0,n+1}$. Then, we have $c_{2^{N-1}+n+1} = q_j = H_{0,n+1}$ and

$$d_{2^{N-1}+n+1} = c_{2^{N-1}+n+1} + d_1 = H_{0,n+1} + d_1 = H_{1,n+1}.$$

Case 2. $\varepsilon_0 = 0, t > 1$. Applying Lemma 2, we get that $p_i > q_j$, thus from Lemma 1 we have $\min\{q_j, d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}\} = \min\{p_i, c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}\} = c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}$. On the other hand, it follows from Lemma 2 that $s_l < t_k$, thus by Lemma 1, we have

$$\min\{s_l, d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}\} = \min\{t_k, c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}\}$$

$$= c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}.$$

Assume that $c_{2^{N-1}+n+1} = d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}$. Then, we have

$$\begin{aligned} c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1} &= d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1} \\ &= 2d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1} \\ &> d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1} \geq \min\{s_l, d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}\}, \end{aligned}$$

which is a contradiction. It follows from Lemma 2 that $c_{2^{N-1}+n+1} = q_j = H_{0,n+1}$ and

$$\begin{aligned} c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1} &= d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1} \\ &= H_{1,n+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1} = \min\{s_l, d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}\} \\ &= \min\{2d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + 2d_{2^{N-1}+1}, d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}\}. \end{aligned}$$

Since

$$\begin{aligned} d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1} \\ < 2d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + 2d_{2^{N-1}+1}, \end{aligned}$$

it follows that $d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1} = H_{1,n+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1}$, thus we have $d_{2^{N-1}+n+1} = H_{1,n+1}$.

Case 3. $\varepsilon_0 = 1$. Applying Lemma 3, we get that $q_j > p_i$, thus from Lemma 1, we have $\min\{p_i, c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}\} = \min\{q_j, d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}\} = d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}$. On the other hand, it follows from Lemma 3 that $s_l > t_k$, thus by Lemma 1, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \min\{t_k, c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}\} &= \min\{s_l, d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}\} \\ &= d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}. \end{aligned}$$

Assume that $c_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1} = d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1}$. Then, we have $d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1} = d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+1} + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}$, thus we have $d_{2^{N-1}+n+1} = d_1 + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}$. It follows that $d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+1} = 2d_1 + c_{2^{N-1}+n+1} = \min\{p_i, c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}\}$, which is a contradiction because $d_1 > 0$. Then, we have

$$d_{2^{N-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1} = t_k = d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + 2d_{2^{N-1}+1}.$$

It follows that

$$d_{2^{N-1}+n+1} = d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1} = H_{1,n+1}.$$

Applying Lemma 1 and Lemma 3, we get that

$$\begin{aligned} d_1 + d_{2^{N-1}+n+1} &= H_{0,n+1} \\ &= d_1 + d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1} \\ &= \min\{p_i, c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}\} \\ &= \min\{2d_{2^{i_1-1}+1} + d_{2^{i_2-1}+1} + \dots + d_{2^{i_t-1}+1} + d_{2^{N-1}+1}, c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}\} \\ &= c_{2^{N-1}+n+1}, \end{aligned}$$

thus we have $c_{2^{N-1+n+1}} = H_{0,n+1}$. The proof of Theorem 4 has been completed.

5. Proof of Theorem 6

First we prove that for

$$H = H(1, 2, 4, 8, \dots, 2^{2l-1}, 2^{2l} - 1, 2^{2l+1} - 1, 2(2^{2l+1} - 1), 4(2^{2l+1} - 1), 8(2^{2l+1} - 1), \dots),$$

$C = H_0$ and $D = H_1$, we have $C \cup D = \mathbb{N}$, $C \cap D = 2^{2l} - 1 + (2^{2l+1} - 1)\mathbb{N}$ and $R_C(m) = R_D(m)$. It is easy to see that for $H' = H(h_1, h_2, \dots, h_{2l+1}) = H(1, 2, 4, 8, \dots, 2^{2l-1}, 2^{2l} - 1)$, $C' = H'_0$ and $D' = H'_1$, we have $C' \cup D' = [0, 2^{2l+1} - 2]$ and $C' \cap D' = \{2^{2l} - 1\}$ because

$$2^{2l} - 1 = h_{2l+1} = h_1 + h_2 + \dots + h_{2l} = 1 + 2 + 4 + \dots + 2^{2l-1}.$$

Furthermore, for $H'' = H(2^{2l+1} - 1, 2(2^{2l+1} - 1), 4(2^{2l+1} - 1), 8(2^{2l+1} - 1), \dots)$, $C'' = H''_0$ and $D'' = H''_1$, we have $C'' \cup D'' = (2^{2l+1} - 1)\mathbb{N}$ and $C'' \cap D'' = \emptyset$, which implies $C \cup D = \mathbb{N}$ and $C \cap D = 2^{2l} - 1 + (2^{2l+1} - 1)\mathbb{N}$. Moreover, by Theorem 3, $R_C(m) = R_D(m)$ for every positive integer m . On the other hand, let us suppose that for some sets C and D , we have $C \cup D = \mathbb{N}$ and $C \cap D = r + m\mathbb{N}$. By Conjecture 2, we may assume that for some Hilbert cube $H(h_1, h_2, \dots)$, we have $C = H_0$ and $D = H_1$. We have to prove the existence of integer l such that $h_i = 2^{i-1}$ for $1 \leq i \leq 2l$, $h_{2l+1} = 2^{2l} - 1$ and $h_{2l+2+j} = 2^j(2^{2l+1} - 1)$ for every nonnegative integer j . We may suppose that $h_1 = 1$ and $h_2 = 2$. Consider the Hilbert cube $H(1, 2, 4, \dots, 2^u, h_{u+2}, \dots)$, where $h_{u+2} \neq 2^{u+1}$. Let us write $v = h_{u+2}$. We will prove that $v = 2^{u+1} - 1$. Assume that $v > 2^{u+1}$. Then, it is clear that $2^{u+1} \notin H$ because $1 + 2 + \dots + 2^u = 2^{u+1} - 1 < 2^{u+1}$. Thus, we have $v < 2^{u+1}$ i.e., $v \leq 2^{u+1} - 1$. Assume that $v \leq 2^{u+1} - 2$. Considering v as a one term sum, it follows that $v \in D$. Moreover, if $v = \sum_{i=0}^u \lambda_i 2^i$, $\lambda_i \in \{0, 1\}$, then $\sum_{i=0}^u \lambda_i$ must be even; otherwise, v would have two different representations from D . It follows that $v \in C$ and $v + 1 = h_1 + h_{u+2} \in C$. Furthermore, if we have a representation $v + 1 = \sum_{i=0}^u \delta_i 2^i$, $\delta_i \in \{0, 1\}$, then $\sum_{i=0}^u \delta_i$ must be odd; otherwise, v would have two different representations from C . This implies that $v + 1 \in D$, thus we have $v, v + 1 \in C \cap D$. It follows that $C \cap D = \{v, v + 1, \dots\}$ is an arithmetic progression with common difference 1. This implies that the generating functions of the sets C and D are of the form

$$C(z) = p(z) + \frac{z^v}{1 - z},$$

where $p(z)$ is a polynomial, and

$$D(z) = q(z) + \frac{z^v}{1 - z},$$

where $q(z)$ is a polynomial, and

$$p(z) + q(z) = 1 + z + z^2 + \dots + z^{v-1} = \frac{1 - z^v}{1 - z}.$$

Since $R_C(n) = R_D(n)$, we have $C^2(z) - D^2(z) = C(z^2) - D(z^2)$. It follows that

$$\left(p(z) + \frac{z^v}{1 - z}\right)^2 - \left(q(z) + \frac{z^v}{1 - z}\right)^2 = p(z^2) + \frac{z^{2v}}{1 - z^2} - q(z^2) - \frac{z^{2v}}{1 - z^2},$$

which implies

$$p^2(z) - q^2(z) + \frac{2z^v}{1 - z}(p(z) - q(z)) = p(z^2) - q(z^2).$$

Thus we have

$$(p(z) - q(z)) \cdot \frac{1 + z^v}{1 - z} = p(z^2) - q(z^2).$$

We get

$$(p(z) - q(z)) \cdot (1 + z^v) = (p(z^2) - q(z^2)) \cdot (1 - z).$$

The leading coefficient in one side is -1 and the other side is 1 , which is a contradiction. Thus we get that $v = 2^{u+1} - 1$. It follows that the Hilbert cube is of the form $H(1, 2, 4, 8, \dots, 2^u, 2^{u+1} - 1, \dots)$. As $h_{u+2} = 2^{u+1} - 1 = 1 + 2 + \dots + 2^u = h_1 + h_2 + \dots + h_{u+1}$, and $2^{u+1} - 1$ is regarded as a one-term sum contained in D , we have $u + 1$ must be even, i.e., $u + 1 = 2l$. It follows that there exists an integer l such that $h_i = 2^{i-1}$ for $1 \leq i \leq 2l$ and $h_{2l+1} = 2^{2l} - 1$. It follows that $2^{2l} - 1 \in C \cap D$ and $r = 2^{2l} - 1$.

We apply induction on j to show that $h_{2l+2+j} = 2^j(2^{2l+1} - 1)$ for every nonnegative integer j . For $j = 0$, take the Hilbert cube of the form $H(1, 2, 4, 8, \dots, 2^{2l-1}, 2^{2l} - 1, h_{2l+2}, \dots)$. Write $w = h_{2l+2}$. We prove that $w = 2^{2l+1} - 1$. Suppose that $w > 2^{2l+1} - 1$. Since $1 + 2 + \dots + 2^{2l-1} + 2^{2l} - 1 < 2^{2l+1} - 1$, it follows that $2^{2l+1} - 1 \notin H = C \cup D$, which is impossible. Therefore, $w \leq 2^{2l+1} - 1$. Suppose that $w \leq 2^{2l+1} - 3$. We will show that $w \in C \cap D$. Obviously, w is a one-term sum contained in D . Since w has a representation from $H(h_1, \dots, h_{2l+1})$, w must be an element of C ; otherwise, w would have two different representations from D , which is absurd. In the next step, we prove $w + 1 \in C \cap D$. Obviously, $w + 1 = h_1 + h_{2l+2}$ as a two-term sum contained in C . Since $w + 1$ can be written in terms of the Hilbert cube $H(h_1, \dots, h_{2l+1})$ and $w + 1 \leq 2^{2l+1} - 2$, we have $w + 1 \in D$. It follows that $w, w + 1 \in C \cap D$, which is a contradiction. It follows that the only possible values of w are $w = 2^{2l+1} - 2$, and $w = 2^{2l+1} - 1$. Suppose that $w = 2^{2l+1} - 2$. Then, it is clear that $w \in D$. On the other hand, $2^{2l} - 2 = 1 + 2 + \dots + 2^{2l-1} + 2^{2l} - 1 = h_1 + h_2 + \dots + h_{2l+1}$, where in the right hand side, there are $2l + 1$ terms, which is impossible. Thus we have $w = 2^{2l+1} - 1$. In this case,

$2^{2l} - 1, (2^{2l} - 1) + (2^{2l+1} - 1) \in C \cap D, (C \cap D) \cap \{1, 2, \dots, 2^{2l+1} - 1\} = \{2^{2l} - 1\}$. It follows that $m \mid 2^{2l+1} - 1$. If $m \leq \frac{2^{2l+1} - 1}{2}$, then $(C \cap D) \cap \{1, 2, \dots, 2^{2l+1} - 1\} \neq \{2^{2l} - 1\}$, a contradiction. Then, we have $r = 2^{2l} - 1$ and $m = 2^{2l+1} - 1$.

In the induction step, we assume that for some k , we know that $h_{2l+2+j} = 2^j(2^{2l+1} - 1)$ holds for $j = 0, 1, \dots, k$, and we prove $h_{2l+2+k+1} = 2^{k+1}(2^{2l+1} - 1)$. Let $H^{(k)} = H(1, 2, 4, 8, \dots, 2^{2l-1}, 2^{2l} - 1, 2^{2l+1} - 1, 2(2^{2l+1} - 1), 4(2^{2l+1} - 1), 8(2^{2l+1} - 1), \dots, 2^k(2^{2l+1} - 1))$, $C^{(k)} = H_0^{(k)}$ and $D^{(k)} = H_0^{(k)}$. Then

$$C^{(k)} \cap D^{(k)} = \{2^{2l} - 1 + i(2^{2l+1} - 1) : i = 0, 1, \dots, 2^k - 1\}.$$

If $C = H_0(1, 2, 4, 8, \dots, 2^{2l-1}, 2^{2l} - 1, 2^{2l+1} - 1, 2(2^{2l+1} - 1), 4(2^{2l+1} - 1), 8(2^{2l+1} - 1), \dots, 2^k(2^{2l+1} - 1), h_{2l+2+k+1}, \dots)$, then $C \cap D = \{e_1, e_2, \dots\}$, where $e_i = 2^{2l} - 1 + (i - 1)(2^{2l+1} - 1)$ for $i \geq 1$, and $e_{2^{k+1}+1} = 2^{2l} - 1 + 2^{k+1}(2^{2l+1} - 1)$. Furthermore, $e_{2^{k+1}+1} = 2^{2l} - 1 + h_{2l+1+k+1}$, and then $h_{2l+1+k+1} = 2^{k+1}(2^{2l+1} - 1)$, which completes the proof.

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